

THE PRIMARY STUDY ON THE FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF C/Al COMPOSITES

Chen Rong, Wu Renjie and Zhang Guo Ding
(Institute of Composite Materials, Shanghai Jiao Tong
University, Shanghai, China)

ABSTRACT

The fatigue behaviors of three kinds of composite wires with different interface bonding states have been studied. The specimens were fabricated by the method of CVD to form Ti-B coating on the surface of carbon fibers and then infiltrated with the molten aluminum alloy. It is found in the experiments that fatigue S-N curves show the trend that the fatigue life increase linearly with decreasing the fatigue load, no definitive endurance limit is obvious. It is possible for composite to fatigue failure after the number of 10^7 cycles. The evidence of fiber damage may be in one or more forms such as the failure of fiber-matrix interface, matrix cracking or crazing, fiber breaking and void growth. The different interface bonding states result in appearance of varied fatigue fracture forms. Although initial damage may appear very early in the fatigue life, its propagation may be arrested by the internal structure of composite with suitable interface bonding, increasing the fatigue life. Composite is insensitive to the presence of initial microscopic flaws and defects, voids, and fiber breaks, etc, so fatigue resistance of the composite is better than that of metal.

INTRODUCTION

With the development of composite fabricated technique, the study on fatigue behavior of composite become more and more important. In service, fatigue loads are usually unavoidable, for this reason recent designs do not specify static strength alone as a design criterion, but also include fatigue analysis. The demand for improved performance of structural materials in transportation industries, particularly in aircraft, makes fatigue analysis an important consideration. But clear design criterion, similar to the ones that exist for fatigue of metal has not yet been established. With better specific stiffness, specific strength and some excellent properties in high temperature, metal matrix composite will take a more important role in future aviation materials. So It's useful to study the fatigue behavior of composite.

The fact that composite possess better fatigue property is determined by its internal structure. Because of fatigue crack propagations are arrested by fiber-matrix interface, the ratio of fatigue strength at 10^7 cycles to its tensile strength is about 40-50% in metal and 60-80% in composite.

There exists various factors influenced on the fatigue behavior of composite. As the factors of materials itself as concerns, the interface bonding of composite is very important. The fatigue behaviors of composite are varies with the different interface bonding which due to appearance of different fatigue failure patterns. In order to study

the fatigue behavior of composite in different interface bonding states, we elect composite wire as specimen. Because in the process of fabrication of composite precursor wire, the time of carbon fiber infiltrated with molten aluminum is much short, usually in about 2 seconds. The chemical reaction between carbon fiber and aluminum is not serious. So the interface bonding is in a moderate state, and can be changed by some means of various of different methods, such as heat exposure treatment and thermal cycling. But the interface bonding of composite laminates is very strong at original condition, since the common fabrication process of composite plates is conducted by hot press C/Al precursor wires and Al foils in vacuum for a considerably long time, so it is difficult to systematic study the fatigue property of composite plate at different inter-

Fig.1 Small self-made high frequency fatigue testing machine

face bonding. Since the diameter of composite wire is small, usually in 0.4-0.5mm, and tensile load is about 20kg, no ready-made fatigue test machine can be used. So we specially designed and fabricated a small fatigue test machine to be used as testing the fatigue property of composite wires. The outline of this machine is shown as in Fig.(1).

EXPERIMENTAL

The specimen used in this study are three kinds of composite wires fabricated by the method of CVD to form Ti-B coating on the carbon fibers and then infiltrated with molten aluminum alloy. Matrix used are Al-Ti alloy, LD₂ and LD₁₀ alloy respectively, reinforced with Model T300 carbon fiber. The specimen is about 50% fiber volume fraction and about 100mm length and 0.5 mm in diameter. In the testing process, the reinforcement paper having dimension of 25 mm length, 15 mm width and 0.2 mm thick is cohered in the end of the specimen in order to prevent slip between the grip and specimen. A good result is gotten. These tests are conducted on the self-made fatigue machine at the frequency of 100Hz. The specimen was in tensile-tensile condition under sinusoidal load control. Failure was taken as complete separation. The stress ratio R is about 0.5.

Self-made shear machine, was used to test longitudinal shear strength of composite wires in three kinds of different matrix so as to compare their interface bonding strength. The fatigue fracture feature was investigated by means of TEM in order to study the fatigue crack propagation behavior in the composite.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The number of fatigue cycles to fatigue were recorded at four stress levels when the specimens were under tensile-tensile fatigue load at frequency of 100Hz. The specimen remain unfracture at the lowest stress level above 10^7 cycles. The fatigue S-N curves of composite wire are

shown in Fig.2. All has a negative slope. That is the fatigue life of composite increase as decreasing the stress level. The S-N curves are basically linear from the scatter of date. The fatigue fracture strength is larger for T300/Al-Ti composite wire with large tensile strength, the ratio of fatigue strength at 10^7 cycles to tensile strength is about 65%. For T300/LD₂ and T300/LD₁₀, the ratio is about 80% and 58% respectively.

Self-made shear testing machine is used to test the longitudinal shear strength of three kinds of composite wires. Specimens seperated in the interface during the test. So longitudinal shear is related with the strength of the interface bonding, and increase as the bonding strength increase. As the result of the shear experiment which is coincident with the one found through the investigation by TEM, the interface bonding of T300/Al-Ti composite wires is the weakest, T300/LD₂ becomes comparatively strong and T300/LD₁₀ is the most strong. some machanical properties of three kinds of composite wires are shown in Table 1.

Fig.2 The fatigue S-N curves of T300/Al-Ti, T300/LD₂ and T300/LD₁₀ composite wires.

The fatigue failure of composite is the result from varied fatigue damage modes which occur partly or on the whole in the fatigue process. These modes consist of interface debonding, matrix cracking or crazing and void growth, etc. Different interface bonding result in appearance of these different fracture modes. In metals the appearance of detectable damage is generally considered unsafe, because it rapidly grows to final fracture. In composite materials, however, it is not necessarily so, because although initial damage may appear very early in fatigue life, its propagation may be arrested by the internal structure of the composite.

In the fatigue process, the fatigue crack in T300/Al-Ti composite wires may be occurred due to interface debonding with weak interface bonding. Because its interface is easily crazed in the affect of alternative fatigue stress. The debonding length extend as the number of cycles increase. When the length extend to reach a certain degree, weak points of the fiber embed in the matrix in original are emerged because of sepa-

ration of fiber and matrix. Which produce favourable condition for fiber breaking in the weak point at the stress level less than the strength of fiber. There exists a large quantity of fiber pull-out scattered in the fatigue fracture feature as shown in Fig.3. The homogeneous scatter of fiber pull-out proves that fatigue crack initiated at the every weak points of interface of composite wires before the specimens failure. In another condition, fatigue crack in T300/Al-Ti composite wires may initiated in the matrix. when it propagates to approach the interface, crack branching may take place, which relieve some of the stress concentration in the vicinity of the crack and change the direction that crack propagate perpendicular to the fiber, so enhance the fatigue life. But when the interface bonding is too weak, the tensile splitting will easily occurred in the interface, crack propagate with fast velocity since low interface shear strength. Gouda⁴ pointed out that crack propagation velocity is reverse proportional to the interface shear strength. The fast velocity of crack propagation result in decreasing fatigue resistance. The fatigue strength of T300/Al-Ti composite wires is 65% of its static strength may be the result of weak interface bonding. But the tensile strength of T300/Al-Ti is high, so the interface bonding state with optimum tensile strength is not the one with optimum fatigue strength. These differences most likely reflect the different failure mechanisms in tensile and fatigue. In the fatigue process, interface is easily damaged to produce fatigue crack in the affection of alternative

Table 1 Tensile Strength, Fatigue Strength at 10^7 Cycles and Longitudinal Shear Strength of Different Matrix Composite Wires

properties specimens	tensile strength (10^7 N/mm^2)	fatigue strength (10^7 N/mm^2)	shear strength (10^7 N/mm^2)	fatigue strength / tensile strength
T300/Al-Ti	95	62	1.6	65%
T300/LD ₂	55	44	2.8	80%
T300/LD ₁₀	38	22	4.3	58%

fatigue. figure 5 shows the development of transverse cracks in T300/LD₂ composite wire after 10^6 cycles. So when tensile splitting become the main mode of fatigue fracture, the interface bonding must be increase in order to hamper the tensile splitting or debonding in the interface and decrease the crack propagation velocity parallel to the direction of fiber. But this kind of interface bonding strength may be result in crack propagation perpendicular to the direction of fiber in the tensile condition and decrease tensile strength. So for the interface bonding of T300/Al-Ti composite wire, increasing its bonding will increase the ratio of fatigue strength at 10^7 cycles to its static strength.

The fatigue fracture feature of T300/LD₂ composite wire with stronger interface bonding are shown in Figure 4,6. The fatigue crack propagate basically perpendicular to the direction of load. Fatigue crack was initiated in the weak point of composite wire. When fatigue crack in the matrix approach a fiber, high stress ahead of the crack tip affect the fibers, make the brittle fiber ahead of crack break abruptly. A larger shear strength was produced in the fiber-matrix interface by the break of fiber. Shear crack grow in the vicinity of the matrix in the direction of perpendicular to fiber because of strong interface bonding and then approaches the fiber again. Crack propagation perpendicular to the direction of load result in composite wires fatigue fracture in low stress level. Since the interface bonding of T300/LD₂ is not very strong, debonding between fiber and matrix will occur when fatigue crack appro-

Fig. 3,4 The fatigue fracture of T300/Al-Ti and T300/LD₂ composite wires after 10⁶ cycles

Fig.5 Transverse cracks in T300/LD₂ after 10⁶ fatigue cycles.

aches the interface in some areas. So crack propagate in the direction of parallel to load which nampers the trend of fast propagation of the crack and increase fatigue resistance. There are many steps shown in Fig.4, fracture didn't occurred in the same plane. Every step is the result of interface debonding which make crack propagate in longitudinal direction and provide a favourable condition for increasing the fatigue

Fig.6,7 The fatigue fracture feature of T300/LD₂ and T300/LD₁₀ composite wires after 7x10⁶ and 10⁵ cycles respectively.

resistance. The tensile fracture feature of this kinds of composite wire is plate without step appearance. so interface easily debonded under the control of alternative stress in the fatigue process.

The interface bonding of T300/LD₁₀ is very strong. Once crack initiated in the interface, it can penetrate the fiber to propagate fast by break-

ing fiber and then result in the fracture of the whole material. There are no fiber pull out and step shown in the fatigue fracture feature in Fig.7. Its fracture plane is very plate, so fatigue strength of this kind of composite wire is poor.

Here we may draw the following conclusions.

A. Fatigue property of C/Al composite is better than that of metal. The fatigue strength of three kinds of composite wires T300/Al-Ti, T300/LD₂ and T300/LD₁₀ are 65%,80% and 58% of their static strength respectively. Fatigue S-N²curves are basically linear. No definitive endurance limit is obvious.

B. The different interface bonding states affect the fatigue properties distinctly. Composite wire in the weak interface bonding have better fatigue property. Because fatigue crack propagatè in the direction of parallel to load in the fiber-matrix interface. Fatigue resistance is poor when interface bonding is strong because of crack propagation perpendicular to the direction of load.

C. The fatigue property of composite wire can be increased by changing the interface bonding into a suitable state. The interface bonding respond to optimum tensile strength will not necessarily result in optimum fatigue property. It is easy for interface to debonding under alternative fatigue stress.

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